

A Study of the Complexation Reaction between Gallium and Calmagite

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Gallium is found to form violet coloured complex with calmagite, i.e., 3-hydroxy-4-[(6-hydroxy-*m*-tolyl) azo]-1-napthalene sulfonic acid. A detailed study about the chelation reaction of gallium with calmagite is made. The studies about the nature and number of complexes formed show the formation of only one complex. The composition of the complex formed, as determined by various methods, was found to be 1 : 2 (metal : reagent). The values of $\log K$ were calculated by various methods at four different fixed values of ionic strength. The value of thermodynamic stability constant has been obtained by plotting $\log K$ against ionic strength and extrapolating the curves so obtained to zero ionic strength. A tentative suggestion about the structure of the chelate has also been made. A suitable procedure has also been recommended for the photometric determination of gallium with calmagite giving various conditions of study in detail.

Calmagite i.e., 3-hydroxy-4-[(6-hydroxy-*m*-tolyl)azo]-1-napthalene sulfonic acid, has the following structure

It was first introduced as a stable substitute for Eriochrome Black T in EDTA titrations for calcium and magnesium¹. Since then, it has been largely used for the complexometric determination of calcium and magnesium^{2,3,4}. Its use as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of thorium and magnesium is also known^{5,6,7}. Ingman and Ringbom have reported equilibrium constant values of calcium and magnesium complexes with this reagent⁸.

1. F. Lindstrom and R. Issac, *Talanta*, 1966, 13, 1003.
2. F. Lindstrom and H. Diehl, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 1123.
3. H. Diehl, *Chem. Abst.*, 62 : 13850d.
4. H. Diehl and J. Ellingboe, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 1120.
5. P. J. Curcio and P. F. Lott, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1962, 26, 487.
6. H. Diehl, R. Olsen, G. I. Spielholtz and R. Jensen, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, 35, 1144.
7. R. Olsen and H. Diehl, *Anal. Chem.*, 1963, 35, 1142.
8. F. Ingman and A. Ringbom, *Microchem. J.*, 1966, 10, 545.

The present paper deals with the chelation reaction of gallium with calmagite (abbreviated as CLM) and reports for the first time the complex formation, composition of the complex formed, values of $\log K$ as calculated at different fixed values of ionic strength and other analytical aspects of the system.

EXPERIMENTAL

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with Beckman model B spectrophotometer, operated on stabilized 110 V AC and using 1 cm glass cells. In all measurements, distilled water was used as a blank. For pH measurements, Beckman direct reading H-2 model pH meter, with glass calomel electrode system was used.

The solution of Ga(III) was obtained by dissolving Gallium Chloride (Johnson Matthey and Company) in distilled water acidified with suitable acid. Calmagite (Standard Fluka) solution was prepared by dissolving known weight of pure sample in distilled water.

All experiments were performed at 25°. In all cases, total volume maintained was 25 ml.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of pH on the reagent : The variation in $\lambda_{\max}$ with change in pH of reagent alone was studied by taking $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ solution. These solutions were adjusted to different pH values and their absorption spectra was studied in the entire visible range of the spectrum. The results obtained are tabulated below :

TABLE 1 .

Effect of pH on $\lambda_{\max}$ of Calmagite

pH	$\lambda_{\max}$ (m μ)
1.0- 6.0	550
6.5- 9.0	580
9.5-11.5	630
12.0	580

The dissociation of Calmagite may be given as below :

The pK values of calmagite, determined spectrophotometrically, were found to be 8.2 and 11.5. The $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group present in the molecule dissociates at much lower pH and so its dissociation could not be determined. The values obtained in the present work are in good agreement with the values reported earlier by Lindstorm and Diehl², which are 8.14 and 12.35.

Characteristics of the chelate formed : The nature and number of complexes formed was determined by preparing three series of solutions containing different ratios of reagent : metal (c'/c) as 4 : 1, 1 : 1 and 1 : 4. The nine mixtures in each series were adjusted to different

pH values and absorption spectra was studied over entire visible range. The results obtained are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

*Absorption spectra of Calmagite chelate concentration of gallium chloride = $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$
Concentration of calmagite = $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$*

System	Ratio reagent : metal	λ_{max} (m μ) at pH						
		1.0	2.0	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	8.0
Ga (III)-	4 : 1	550	570	570	570	570	570	580
CLM	1 : 1	550	570	570	570	570	570	580
	1 : 4	550	570	570	570	570	570	580

The above table shows that for Ga(III)—Calmagite chelate, λ_{max} is 570 m μ in the pH range of 2.0 to 6.0. It also shows only one shift in λ_{max} indicating that only one complex is formed. For actual experiment, pH and wavelengths of study chosen were 5.0 and 590 m μ and 600 m μ respectively at which the difference in absorbance of reagent alone and chelate is considerable.

Composition of the chelate : The composition of the Ga(III)-Calmagite chelate was studied by three different methods—(i) Job's method of continuous variations using equimolecular solutions, (ii) mole ratio method and (iii) slope ratio method.

All the three methods show Ga(III)-Calmagite chelate to have 1 : 2 composition (metal : reagent) at pH 5.0 and at 590 m μ and 600 m μ .

Calculation of the stability constant : In the complexation reaction of Ga³⁺ with Calmagite, the following equilibria is considered to be present

The study is made at pH 5.0 and hence the hydrolysis of gallium cannot be ruled out. But, as the values of stability constant are fairly high for the complex, it was assumed that effect of hydrolysis on the stability constant value is negligible.

The calculation of log K from absorbance measurements was determined by three different methods—(i) method of Anderson and coworkers modified by Dey and coworkers^{9,10}, (ii) mole ratio method¹¹, and (iii) Job's method of continuous variations using non equimolecular solutions¹².

The values of concentrations used for the calculation of log K by various methods are given below. The experiments were done at four different fixed values of ionic strength (μ) maintained by addition of suitable quantity of potassium chloride solution.

9. R. T. Foley and R. C. Anderson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1195; 1949, 71, 909.

10. A. K. Mukherji and A. K. Dey, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314; *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1958, 18, 324.

11. J. H. Yoe and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111

12. P. Job, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.

TABLE 3

Concentrations of the components used for the calculation of log K by the method (a)

System	μ	$c \times 10^5$ (M)	$p(c'/c)$
Ga(III)—CLM	0.05, 0.10	13.33	1.0
	0.15 and 0.20	10.00	1.0
		8.00	1.0

TABLE 4

Values of concentrations, E_m , E_s and α for the calculation of log K by the method (b)

System	μ	$c' \times 10^5$ (M)	E_m	E_s	α
Ga(III)—CLM	0.05	2.66	0.305	0.290	0.050
		2.50	0.272	0.260	0.049
	0.10	2.66	0.305	0.287	0.056
		2.50	0.272	0.258	0.056
	0.15	2.66	0.300	0.282	0.060
		2.50	0.270	0.254	0.060
	0.20	2.66	0.300	0.280	0.066
		2.50	0.270	0.252	0.066

TABLE 5

Values of concentrations and p for the calculation of log K by the method (c)

System	μ	$c \times 10^4$ (M)	p	vol. of metal ion at peak (ml)
Ga(III)—CLM	0.05	0.677 and 0.625	2.0	9.8
		1.33 and 1.25	0.5	4.2
	0.10	0.677 and 0.625	2.0	9.7
		1.33 and 1.25	0.5	4.25
	0.15	0.677 and 0.625	2.0	9.6
		1.33 and 1.25	0.5	4.3
	0.20	0.677 and 0.625	2.0	9.5
		1.33 and 1.25	0.5	4.4

A typical set of graphs obtained in the calculation of stability constant is given (Fig. 1-4).

The following table summarizes the results obtained of stability constant values by various methods.

TABLE 6

Values of stability constant of Calmagite chelate
 temperature = 25°, composition of the chelate 1 : 2 [Ga(III) : CLM]

System	μ	log K	method
Ga(III)—Calmagite	0.05	11.8±0.1	(a)
		12.5±0.1	(b)
		11.9±0.1	(c)
	0.10	11.5±0.1	(a)
		12.3±0.1	(b)
		11.4±0.1	(c)
	0.15	11.2±0.1	(a)
		12.2±0.1	(b)
		11.0±0.1	(c)
0.20	11.0±0.1	(a)	
	12.0±0.1	(b)	
	10.7±0.1	(c)	

(a) = Dey *et al.* method.

(b) = mole ratio method.

(c) = method of continuous variations.

Fig. 1. Concentration of the components used for the calculation of log K by the method of Dey and co-workers. $\text{pH} = 5.0$, $\lambda = 590 \text{ m}\mu$, $\mu = 0.1$.

Concentration of Ga(III) and Calmagite

curve A : $13.33 \times 10^{-5} M$

curve B : $10.00 \times 10^{-5} M$

curve C : $8.00 \times 10^{-5} M$

Fig. 2. Values of concentrations for the calculation of $\log K$ by mole ratio method. $pH = 5.0$, $\lambda = 590 m\mu$, $\mu = 0.1$.

Concentration of Calmagite

curve A : $2.66 \times 10^{-5} M$

curve B : $2.50 \times 10^{-5} M$

Figs. 3 and 4. Concentrations of the components used for the calculation of $\log K$ by the method of continuous variations. $pH = 5.0$, $\lambda = 590 m\mu$, $\mu = 0.1$.

Concentration of $Ga(III)$

Fig. 3

curve A : $0.67 \times 10^{-4} M$, $p = 2.0$

curve B : $1.33 \times 10^{-4} M$, $p = 0.5$

Fig. 4

curve A : $0.625 \times 10^{-4} M$, $p = 2.0$

curve B : $1.25 \times 10^{-4} M$, $p = 0.5$

To obtain the value of thermodynamic stability constant, a graph of $\log K$ against ionic strength was plotted and the curves so obtained were extrapolated to zero ionic strength (Fig. 5). The value obtained is $= 12.4 \pm 0.2$.

Fig. 5. Extrapolation of the curves of $\log K$ against μ (ionic strength) to obtain the value of thermodynamic stability constant.

The value obtained is $= 12.4 \pm 0.2$.

Position of the chelate ring : The suggestion about the chelate ring can also be made. There are two identical positions for chelation in Calmagite. These are through phenolic oxygen and an azo nitrogen assuming the dissociation of $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ group. The chelation may occur through any one of these positions. This possibility of chelate ring suggests anionic nature to the chelate. The anionic nature was actually observed by adsorption of colour of the chelate an Amberlite IR-45(OH) resin and electrophoresis experiments.

Analytical studies of the chelate : The violet colour of the chelate appears instantaneously. However, the mixtures were kept for half an hour for equilibration. The colour intensity of the chelate is stable even after 48 hrs of standing at room temperature. For maintaining pH to 5.0 in analytical studies, potassium hydrogen phthalate-NaOH buffer was used. The colour intensity of the chelate is stable in the temperature range of 10° to 40° . The effect of reagent concentration was studied and it was observed that at least five fold excess of reagent is necessary to have maximum colour formation.

Sensitivity and Molecular absorption coefficient : The values of sensitivity were found to be $0.35 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (practical) and $0.035 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ (Sandell). The value of molar absorption coefficient was found to be 20,800. This shows that the reagent is quite sensitive to be used as a colorimetric reagent for spectrophotometric determination of gallium(III) in aqueous solution.

Range of adherence to Beer's law : The concentration range of gallium ion within which Beer's law is followed was found out. It was observed that Beer's law holds good in the concentration range of 0.55 to 2.15 ppm of gallium for Ga(III)-Calmagite system at pH 5.0 and 580 m μ .

Effect of diverse ions : A large number of standard solutions of anions and cations were prepared. The effect of these ions on the absorbance of the system was studied. The tolerance limit has been chosen for that concentration of metal ion at which a change of $\pm 2\%$ in the absorbance of the system is observed. It was found that Cu^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Tl^{3+} , UO_3^{2+} and Ce^{4+} interfere at all concentrations.

Procedure recommended for spectrophotometric determination: To the gallium ion solution containing 0.6 to 2.1 ppm of gallium, add five fold excess of Calmagite. For maintaining pH to 5.0, potassium hydrogen phthalate-NaOH buffer is to be used. Allow the mixture to stand for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr and then measure absorbance at 580 m μ . The concentration of an unknown sample solution can be obtained by comparing absorbance of an unknown solution with the calibration curve obtained earlier.

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